

ISSN 2349-5189

2349-5189

LangLit

An International Peer-Reviewed
Open Access Journal

Volume 10 Issue 4

May 2024

www.langlit.org

Chief Editor
Prashant Mothe

Indexed

ICI, Google Scholar, Research Gate, Academia.edu,
IBI, IIFC, DRJI

13.	THE RESILIENCE OF HUMANITY IN THE MOVIE VIRUS BY ASHIQ ABU	SREEKESH K S & RUKSANA A P
14.	BILDUNG OR SELF-FORMATION AS A CONCEPT AND ITS PERCEPTION IN THE NATIONAL CURRICULUM FRAMEWORK 2005 AND NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020	MEDHA
15.	THE MEDIAL OF MYSTERY IN THE MOVIE KUMARI BY NIRMAL SAHADEV	SREEKESH K S & HASNA MARIYAM P
16.	EXPLORING DIVERSITY IN DISABILITY DEPICTIONS IN THE MOVIE PERANBU BY RAM AND THE BOOK THE REASON I JUMB BY NAOKI HIGASHIDHA	SREEKESH K S & MUHSINA P H
17.	AN OVERVIEW OF EXPERIENCE OF RACISM IN THE LIGHT OF THE BLACK SKIN, WHITE MASKS BY FRANTZ FANON	DR. INDU SINGH RAJPUT
18.	INFLUENCES INVENT IDENTITIES – SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN SELECTION DAY	R. CHANDRA SEKHAR
19.	TEACHING VOCABULARY AND LISTENING SKILLS THROUGH MOVIE ‘TITANIC’	DR. ASHOK PANDYA
20.	INTEGRATION OF INDIAN KNOWLEDGE SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATION AS ENVISIONED IN NEP 2020:PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES	DR. KAMALAKAR BABURAO GAIKWAD
21.	SITA IN CONTEMPORARY WRITINGS: A FEMINIST READING	DR. SAROJ BALA
22.	A PSYCHOANALYTICAL COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CHARACTERS NIMMI WITH LADY MACBETH AND GHAZALA WITH GERTRUDE IN BHARDWAJ’S MAQBOOL AND HAIDER	AMINA AMBREEN & DR. PRATIMA CHAITANYA
23.	‘GAMING DISCOURSE’ IN THE ABSURD PLAYS OF HAROLD PINTER AND SAMUEL BECKETT	MR. VINEESH VISHWAM & DR. V. UMA DEVI
24.	EXPLORING THE FEMININE VOICE: GARY SNYDER’S ‘MUSE’ AS A SUBSTANCE FOR CONSCIOUSNESS AND CULTURAL REFLECTION	DR. PANKAJ BALA SRIVASTAVA
25.	FATIGUE AND STRESS OF PHYSICS TEACHERS IN THE CLASSROOM	VASILEIOS AG. DROUGAS & IFIGENEIA V. DROUGA
26.	SOCIAL AND CULTURAL IMPACT OF COLONIAL PEOPLE ON INDIAN WRITERS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE	DEEPALI KUMAWAT & DR. NILIMA PRAKASH KALE

**TEACHING VOCABULARY AND LISTENING SKILLS THROUGH
MOVIE ‘TITANIC’****DR. ASHOK PANDYA**Assistant professor, PhD Guide,
Department of Management,
Career development cell,
Parul University,
Vadodara, Gujarat.**ABSTRACT**

This paper will try to see how movie ‘Titanic’ can be used to teach vocabulary and listening skills. Researcher has hypothesises that this movie can develop vocabulary and writing skills of students. Researcher also believes that traditional way of of teaching may be less effective compared to teaching through this movie. To test this hypothesises, researcher has conducted test. Students have been divided between control group and experimental group. Pre-test and Post res was taken. Students of control group were taught vocabulary and listening skills through movie ‘Titanic’ and Students of experimental group were taught vocabulary and listening skills through traditional way of teaching. In Posttest It was found that students of controlled group scored more marks compared to experimental group. Therefore researcher concludes that teaching vocabulary and listening skills through movie ‘Titanic’ is more effective than traditional way of teaching.

Keywords: Pre-test, Post-test, Experimental Group, Controlled Group.**Introduction:**

Present experiment tries to focus on acquisition of vocabulary, listening skill from movies. Students get bored when they learn from traditional methodology. Method of 20 century should be different from method of previous teachers. Now we have new students who like to watch movies and web series etc. movies can be integrated in classroom. Then acquisition of language can be very very easy. If students get example from movies and if they learn dialogues and listen to pronunciation from movies, then they can retain their learning for longer period of time. Here researcher has tried to use movie ‘Titanic’ in classroom to teach vocabulary, listening skills. Two groups were made. One is controlled group and another is experimental group. Students of experimental group were taught vocabulary and listening skills through traditional methodology. While students of control group were taught vocabulary and listening skill through movie ‘titanic’ in the classroom and then researcher tried to compare score of post-test of both group experimental and control group. Researcher found that students of control group performed better than students of experimental group. Titanic (1997) is of world-class movie. It is romantic tragedy movie directed, written and co-produced by James Cameron. It is dreamy story of male and female character who belong to different classes of Society. They love each-other but the girl is from a rich class. Rich girl is not supposed to love underprivileged boy in 1912. Titanic begun to sink. Boy saved girl and

dies at the end. Titanic has British accent but when students get a lot of experience to listening to native speakers of English. Understanding to British accent becomes possible.

Hypotheses of Research:

Students can learn vocabulary and listening skills well through movie ‘Titanic’

Students can improve their pronunciation well through movie.

Objectives of research:

- To add significant value in field of ELT
- To Make English learning easy globally
- To break barrier of communication of different speakers

Experiment

To develop listening skills. Students watched movie clip (Jumping scene). Students were instructed in advance to do excise. After movie clip, Students filled the following gaps.

A- Fill the gaps

ROSE: Stay back! Don't come _____ closer!

JACK: Take my hand. I'll pull you back in.

ROSE: No! Stay where you are. I _____ it. I'll let go.

JACK: No you won't.

ROSE: What do you mean no I won't? Don't _____ to tell me what I will and will not do. You don't know me.

JACK: You would have done it already. Now come on, take my hand.

ROSE: You're _____ me. Go away.

After completing above worksheet, Researcher gives the answer key. Students themselves evaluates their answer. It develops listening skills of students, they have to listen and watch very carefully to comprehend dialogues and fill gaps. When students feel it problematic to understand, Researcher slowdowns speed of speaking from VLC. Film clip appeals the attention of students well. If students do not know the meaning of certain words, they are advised to find the meaning of words from the dictionary. Researcher does not provide meaning to words. Students are taught to be independent learner.

1- _____ 2- _____ 3- _____ 4- _____ 5- _____ 6- _____

B- Match words with meaning (Jumping scene)

1- Presume	A-to untie or unbutton the lacing of (shoes, garments, etc.)
2- Distract	B-meaningless
3- Unlace	C- a device having to produce thrust to propel a ship, aircraft, etc.

4- Absurd	D-assume with confidence
5- propellers	E- to draw the attention of (a person) away from something

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____

(C) Make sentence of following words (Jumping scene)

- 1 Presume _____
- 2- Distract _____
- 3- Unlace _____
- 4- Absurd _____
- 5- Propellers _____

Control group displays expansion around 3% in post-test where Post-test of Experimental group indicates growth around 13%. Change is observed much in vocabulary and listening skills...

Finding of research

Present paper finds that films ‘Titanic’ is effective to impart vocabulary and listening skills of students. Students can improve pronunciation. Speaking also can be improved. Students take active participant when they are taught through short films. Students like to learn from short films.

Conclusion

Students are more advanced now. Teachers have to be updated to teach them, Movies can be superior source to teach them. Present test motivate future researcher to discover more. Future research can choice some other students and other films to make experiment. Present research add values in the field of ELT. Educationalists can get advantage of this finding to update their teaching methods.

REFERENCES

1. Birulés-Muntané J, Soto-Faraco S “Watching Subtitled Films Can Help Learning Foreign Languages.” PLOS ONE. 2016
2. Etemadi, Aida, “Effects of Bimodal Subtitling of English Movies on Content Comprehension and Vocabulary Recognition”, International Journal of English Linguistics, Vol. 2, No. 1, 2012.
3. Ebrahimi, Raziye et al, “Advantages and Disadvantages of Input-flood through Watching Movies on learning English: A Case Study”, Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research. Volume 5, Issue 1, 2018
4. Griffee, D. An Introduction to Second Language Research Methods: Design and Data tesl-ej.org, 2012. eBook edition.
5. Hofmann, Judith, “Pixar films, popular culture, and language teaching: The potential of animated films for Teaching English as a Foreign Language” Global Studies of Childhood, Vol.9, 2018